

THE BEHAVIORS OF STRENGTHENED CONCRETE GIRDERS WITH GFRP LAMINATES

Dujun Yang and Shijie Wang

*Department of Structure and Bridge Engineering
Chongqing Institute of Communications
Chongqing City, Sichuan Province, 630074, P.R. China*

SUMMARY: The work described that behaviors of reinforced concrete girders strengthened with GFRP laminates (GFRP/RC girders) that were been investigated by authors. The GFRP/RC girders have more advance properties than reinforced concrete girders. They are distinctly improved such as carrying and crack of reinforced concrete girders. This paper discusses stress-strain curves in composite cross-section, crack controlling and other details.

KEYWORDS: composite, glass fiber reinforce plastic, girder, highway bridge, laminate, reinforced concrete.

INTRODUCTION

The most of existing highway reinforce concrete bridges were built with lower technique specification in China, its total length is about 50% of highway bridges spread all over. As we as known, with the traffic and carrying increasing advanced, many concrete girders of bridges must be rebuilt because of its lower technique specification. It will require more and more money, and a lot of times. Therefore, a lot of effort requirements have been raised to repairing techniques for reinforced concrete girders of highway bridges.

There are many techniques to repair concrete bridge such as prestressed tendon, paste steel plates or welding reinforcing bars at the tensile area of girders. Fiber composites, a kind of new engineering materials, have been used more and more in civil engineering. CFRP composite (carbon fiber reinforce plastic) were used to repair a Swedish prestress concrete highway bridge(1), M.R.Ehsani(2) investigated the possibility of strengthened concrete girders with GFRP laminates (glass fiber reinforced plastic).

According to a government's research contract with the Chongqing Institute of Communications, authors investigated the repairing techniques for reinforced concrete bridges with GFRP laminates in recent years. This paper discusses properties of GFRP/RC girder that are strengthened with GFRP laminates, included the curves of stress-strain in cross-sections, crack control of concrete, contributions of GFRP laminates and other details.

PROPERTIES OF STRESS-STRAIN IN COMPOSITE CROSS-SECTIONS OF GFRP/RC GIRDERS

Reference(3) presented structural details of GFRP/RC girders in which there are author's previously works. GFRP/RC girders are consisted of three materials that are concrete, steel bars, and GFRP laminates. Because of their Young's modules are obviously different, especially modules of GFRP laminates are only 10% of the reinforced bars, so it presents apparently distinguish on the property of stress-strain at the composite cross-section between GFRP/RC girders and RC girders.

Fig.1 GFRP/RC Tested Girders

Fig.2 Stress-Strain Curves of GFRP/RC Girders

For investigating regular pattern of its cross-section, 24 vast-scale ($L = 400$ cm) FRP/RC girders were researched which have various thicknesses of laminates and grades of concrete but there were same reinforcing in the cross-section of girders. The dimensions and models of GFRP/RC girders can be shown as Fig.1, and the typical stress-strain curves of composite cross-section are compared between GFRP/RC girders with variously laminates and RC girders (see Fig.2).

From curves in Fig.2, we can see that stress-strain along the height of GFRP/RC girders is nonlinear when limit state. This is not the same as RC girders. Furtherly, we can discover that strains of steel in these girders are not nearly rising with the strain of GFRP laminates when

the steel bars approach its yield limit. At that time, the stresses in composite beams are distributed among concrete, steel bars and GFRP laminates. In other words, the laminates will carry more strain than steel bars.

ANALYSIS OF LIMIT CARRYING BASED ON GFRP/RC GIRDER'S FLEXURE EXPERIMENTS

We can make a simple mode from the nonlinear curve of stress-strain of section for analysis. According to this mode, we can change nonlinear strain curves in a kind of equivalent line relationship, so obtain equations of nature axis and carrying conveniently throughout relationship of the section.

On the other hand, experience equation based on GFRP/RC tested girders can be described as:

$$Y = \frac{M_f}{M_c} = 1427 \exp(-48626 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \frac{E_h}{E_f} \cdot \frac{x}{t} \cdot \frac{h-0.5x}{h_o-0.5x}) \quad (x \neq 0) \quad (1)$$

Where:

M_f / M_c --- ratio of limit bending moments between GFRP/RC and reinforced concrete girders;

x --- nurture axis position of the reinforced concrete cross-section;

h --- depth of reinforced concrete girder;

t --- thickness of GFRP laminates used on the GFRP/RC girders;

h_o --- distance between the center of gravity of reinforcing bars and the top surface of reinforced concrete girders.

Values of testing and calculating are identical and present that carrying bending moment of beams strengthen by GFRP laminate is usually higher 15-40% than reinforced concrete girders. The strengthen ratio may be change with parameters such as modules of materials, thickness of GFRP laminates, etc.. When the stress of bar and concrete achieve their limit value, strains of GFRP laminates are only 50% of themselves limit strain. therefore, strengths of laminates have more than needed.

CRACK ANALYSIS OF LIMIT CARRYING BASED ON GFRP/RC GIRDER'S FLEXURE EXPERIMENTS

Cracks Compare in Loading Of Flexure Experiments

Tab.1 gives the comparing of two kinds of beams based on flexure test. From the crack comparing of GFRP/RC girders and reinforced concrete girder, we can find different properties of GFRP/RC beams as following:

- a. distances of any two cracks of GFRP/ RC girders are more short;
- b. the number of cracks increasing and breadth of cracks reducing;
- c. when the strain of tensile bars is approach yield limit, the developing speed of concrete cracks is obviously reducing;

- d. main factor of control concrete cracks is thickness of GFRP laminate, others such as the shape and construction of GFRP laminates are not clearly control cracks developing.

Table 1 Aaverage Width of Concrete Cracks δ_f (mm)

load (KN)	95		105		130	
girder type	δ_f	δ_f/δ_0	δ_f	δ_f/δ_0	δ_f	δ_f/δ_0
RC girders	0.190		0.405	δ_f		
RC girders with 5 mm plates	0.130	31.6	0.133	67.2	0.364	----
RC girders with 5 mm U-shapes plates	0.136	28.4	0.165	59.3	0.333	----
RC girders with 8 mm plates	0.108	43.2	0.127	68.6	0.291	----

From the table it can be seen that cracks width of GFRP/RC girder have been obviously reduced with the thickness of laminates, the crack's widths are only about 50-70 percent of crack's width of reinforced concrete girders. This ratio is approach with the strength ratio of the composite cross-section.

Calculating Equation Of Crack Width Of Gfrp/Rc Girders

The cracks developing of general reinforce concrete girder is a very complex process. When reinforced concrete girders are strengthened by GFRP laminate, the girders become a composite cross-section girder, and its concrete cracks developing will change more complex. Up to now, Chinese highway specification use line equation for calculating crack width of concrete girders. But this equation is approach, and it has very great error when cracks have large width. From Tab.1 we known that GFRP/RC girders can carrying larger loading than RC girders, therefore, calculating equation of GFRP/RC girder's crack width is not simple line relationship.

Let equation of crack width is following relationship

$$\delta_{f \max} = f(\alpha \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma \cdot \delta_{o \max}) \quad (2)$$

in which:

$\alpha = \frac{E_h}{E_f}$, it is relationship of materials properties;

$\beta = \frac{S_g}{S_f}$, it is relationship of constructural dimensions of tensile bars and GFRP laminates.

Its physic quality is a ratio of internal paste forces between bars and laminates with concrete. S_g is the circumference of one bar in the girder; S_f is the paste length of GFRP laminate with concrete at composite cross-section;

$\gamma = \frac{a_g}{t}$, it described the dimensions relation between the center (a_g) of bars gravity and the thickness (t) of GFRP laminate;

$\delta_{o \max} = \theta \cdot \delta_{o \max}$, it is calculating crack width of reinforced concrete girder. θ is nondimension factor it may be obtained from test;

$\delta_{f\max}$ -- GFRP/RC girder's maxims crack width.

From the our investigating, nondimension factor θ relationship as following

$$\theta = a \times \exp(b \times \delta_{0\max} / d) \tag{3}$$

in the equation, a and b are experience apparatus from testing, d is diameter of tensile bars. If let

$$x = \alpha \times \beta \times \gamma \times \theta \times \delta_{0\max} \tag{4}$$

Fig.3 relationship of $\delta_{f\max}$ vs. parameters

according to equation (2), and based on approach line relationship between x and $\delta_{f\max}$ (see Fig.3), we can introduce a simple equation of the maxtural crack width of GFRP/RC girders as:

$$\delta_{f\max} = f(x) = 0.058 + 0.086 \times x \tag{5}$$

APPLICATION OF THE TECHNIQUE ON TWO HIGHWAY BRIDGES

The technique of strengthening concrete girders with GFRP laminates have been successfully employed in the reparation of two highway reinforced concrete bridges. One of them is three spans 3×20 m T-girders that has built been for 28 years when it was been repaired. Another

one is located in main line of nation with five spans (5×17 m), total length 101.33 m and about 25m height of piers across the river, it's frequency of flood water was been designed 50 years. Because of tremendous influences of floodwater and earthquake in 1989, it was been only allowed carrying lower 80 KN of automobiles. And it has been built 27 years, original design bearing standard of the old bridge was only about 150 KN automobiles when it was been repaired.

The bearing standard of 300 KN weight automobiles and 800 KN single trailer for second one was been required if it can be repaired. During repairing engineering, traffic must be held because of it is that in main line of nation.

According to equations from this paper, sum up the effects such as moments, shears, width of concrete of the early old cross-sections, GFRP laminates were been employed strengthening 25 T-girders of the bridge which already serious damaged. The thickness of laminates can be varied from equations' (1)~(5). The laminates were been manufactured in plates of 160 mm width and 1580 mm length. For reducing total costs of the repaired engineering, the GFRP plates were been manufactured varied thickness from 10 mm ~ 12 mm along button axis of the reinforced concrete T-girders based on internal forces of composite sections.

The time of repairing engineering was cost about 30 days, in which, the time of repairing 25 pieces T-girders cost only about 10 nights.

After repairing engineering of the bridge completed, it has been test which has the same bearing standard of repairing. Loading tests present:

- Any strains of every material are lower than allowing strain values, and stresses of bars and concrete reduce in the same load levels than non-repairing.
- The strength of GFRP materials has enough and to spare.
- The crack widths of old girders were usually 0.3 mm ~ 0.36 mm when testing loading was 150 KN, but the maxtural crack of repaired girders was only 0.25 mm at the same loading and large cracks have been reduced. When maxtural design loads have been tested, only appeared one crack of 0.26 mm width which is very approach with calculating value by equation's (2)~(5), the error between testing values and calculated expecting value is lower 10 percent.

CONCLUSION

GFRP laminates can be used to repair existed reinforcement concrete highway bridges. Crack's propagation is controlled, and the carrying capability can be raised according to require. The application is easy, and the construtural period is very short. Moreover, the repairing costs can be reduced about 20% compared to general repairing methods.

The equations for calculating the bending capability and maxtural breadth of cracks are very useful since the effects of primary parameters of materials and construtural dimensions have been taken into account. Calculation values agreed very well with the test data.

This paper described one repairing method of reinforced concrete girders with GFRP laminates. The equations for calculating strength of cross-section and especially maxtural width of concrete cracks with GFRP laminate to repairing concrete girders are given, it may be described the contribution of composite materials for composite girders. At last, paper given two applications used this method.

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